

Interaction of Iodine with Donors

YESHWANT K. PURANDARE

Department of Chemistry, State University Agricultural & Technical College,
Farmingdale, New York 11735, U.S.A.

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Cryoscopic and spectroscopic measurements on the iodine complexes with pyridine, β -picoline, aniline, tetrahydrofuran (THF), benzene, nitrobenzene, naphthalene, *m*-dinitrobenzene, diphenylamine, and 1,2-dibromoethylene were conducted in order to determine the degree of complexation. In cyclohexane solution, iodine complexes with pyridine and picoline are found to possess greater stability. The stronger interactions between iodine and donor occur when the solvent donor action is attributable mainly to a particular atom, as in pyridine, picoline, aniline, THF, etc. There is a direct relationship between the halogen solvating capacity and the basicity of the solvent.

RECENT research has shown considerable interest in the reactions of iodine with various solvents. In air, iodine vapors display a characteristic purple color; while solutions of iodine in various solvents exhibit different colors, indicating an interaction between iodine and the solvent molecules. This change in color has been attributed to the formation of molecular complexes between the two.

Early studies in this field were done by Hildebrand¹ who calculated the heat of formation of the ethylacetate-iodine complex. In 1948, Hildebrand proposed that the interaction between iodine and various aromatic solvents is due to the action of π -electrons, and he classified the solvents as 'donors' and halogens as 'acceptors'². He also studied the uv and visible spectra of iodine solutions in various solvents³. It was found that the extent of interaction between iodine and the aromatics increased with the introduction of more and more electron donating groups on the aromatic ring. Smith *et al.*⁴ found pyridine diiodide to be the active component in the Fischer reagent. They isolated the crystals of Py_2I_2 and studied its physical properties. Maki and Plyler⁵ studied the formation constant data for 1:1 pyridine-iodine complex from the 184 cm^{-1} absorption band in ir with cyclohexane as solvent. Average K was found to be $107 \pm 25\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1} = [\text{Py}_2\text{I}_2]/[\text{Py}][\text{I}_2]$. Pyridine and iodine also form an ionic complex, dipyridineiodine heptaoidide, which was isolated by Nevitt⁶. A review article by Kleinberg and Davidson⁷ claims that the iodine solutions in pyridine show increasing conductivity with time. In dilute solutions it is attained fast. An extremely high value for conductance (130-132 units) is found at infinite dilution. They attribute it to the ionisation of the pyridine-iodine complex,

Iodine complexes with various other heterocyclic solvents have been studied. Tamres and Searles⁸ used some saturated cyclic sulphides as solvents. McCullough⁹ employed *s*-trithiane, thiacyclohexane, thiacyclopentane, 1,4-dithiacyclohexane, 1,4-diseleniumcyclohexane, 1-oxa-4-thiocyclohexane, 1-oxa-4-seleniumcyclohexane, 1-thia-4-seleniumcyclohexane, etc. in carbon tetrachloride solutions. He observed that the solvating power of the solvent increases with increasing electronegativity of the hetero atom. This observation has been supported by Glusker¹⁰ and Mulliken¹¹. Zingaro and Tefteller¹² used this reaction to compare the donor properties of the phosphine sulphides.

Frantiello¹³ studied the nmr spectra of iodine complexes with acetone, isomeric butylamines, 2-dimethylaminoethanol, aniline and pyridine. Chemical shift data were measured for these solutions containing 1 *M* iodine at 30°. For aniline, the electron density at 2, 4, 6-positions decreased initially due to presence of a N-atom in the molecule and decreased still further. In pyridine, the α -proton signal remained unchanged, but the β - and γ -proton signals shifted by 4-5 cps to lower field, indicating the more positive character of β - and γ -protons. In addition to these compounds, benzene, xylenes and nitro-compounds were studied in presence of iodine, but no significant shift displacements were observed. Mulliken¹⁴ proposed that the geometry of the iodine-benzene complex is such that the longitudinal axis of the iodine molecule is parallel to the benzene plane, with the center of the halogen molecule on the benzene C_6 axis. Haller¹⁵ studied the ir spectra of iodine solutions in aromatic solvents. It was found that the complex formation between iodine and aromatic enhanced the intensities of the peaks in order of increasing basic character, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 < \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3 < \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2 < \text{C}_6(\text{CH}_3)_6$. However, the author could not distinguish whether the effect is due to complex formation or solvent perturbation. Fergusson¹⁶ proposed

that the intensity changes in the ir peaks are due to complex formation rather than solvent perturbation. From his study of enhanced benzene bands at 992 and 850 cm^{-1} , Fergusson proposed an axial C_{6v} model for the benzene-iodine complex, according to which the halogen axis is coincident with the benzene C_6 axis. This was in contrast with the previous model suggested by Mulliken. Fergusson confirmed this C_{6v} model of the complex by ir studies of iodine solution in C_6D_6 ¹⁷.

Experimental

Cryoscopic measurements on iodine complexes: Cyclohexane was selected as solvent for cryoscopic measurements for two reasons, (i) solutions of iodine in cyclohexane exhibit purple color ($\lambda_{max} = 520 \text{ nm}$) indicating no complex formation between the two, and (ii) convenient freezing point (6.5°) for cyclohexane and its high molal freezing point constant ($20.0 \text{ deg kg mol}^{-1}$).

Cryoscopic measurements were performed in a Dewar flask fitted with a stopper carrying a Philadelphia differential thermometer (1 division = 0.01°) and a manually operated glass stirrer. The Dewar flask was kept immersed in an ice-cold water-bath thermally insulated from outside. Freezing points of solutions in cyclohexane were

determined by plotting the cooling curve from the temperature readings obtained every half-minute.

The concentrations of iodine in solutions were determined by titration against 0.01 *M* sodium thiosulphate. The concentration of pyridine in solutions was determined by titration against 0.01 *M* HCl using bromphenol blue as indicator¹⁸. The molecular weights of pure iodine and various donor substances were determined separately to ensure that neither of these dissociate in cyclohexane. For example, pure iodine showed a molecular weight of 254 ± 10 units and pure pyridine of 79 ± 5 units.

Cryoscopic measurements could not be performed on iodine complexes with aniline, *p*-toluidine, and *N,N*-dimethylaniline due to extremely low solubility of these complexes in cyclohexane. Solutions of these complexes even of the order of 0.005 molal could not be prepared. Lower concentrations than this can not give any appreciable depression in the freezing point.

From the data shown in Table 1 it can be seen that of the donors selected, pyridine, β -picoline and tetrahydrofuran form complexes which can definitely be detected by cryoscopic measurements. All iodine complexes show a great

TABLE 1—CRYOSCOPIC MEASUREMENTS ON SOLUTIONS CONTAINING IODINE AND DONOR

Donor	Molality of donor	Molality of iodine	Total molality	ΔT_f exptl.	ΔT_f assuming no complexation
Pyridine	0.010 88	0.004 16	0.015 04	0.220	0.301
	0.009 12	0.009 78	0.018 90	0.220	0.378
	0.016 30	0.007 15	0.023 45	0.300	0.469
	0.018 07	0.018 26	0.036 33	0.390	0.727
β -Picoline	0.010 0	0.010 0	0.020 0	0.222	0.400
	0.015 0	0.015 0	0.030 0	0.325	0.600
	0.020 0	0.020 0	0.040 0	0.412	0.800
Tetrahydrofuran	0.010 0	0.010 0	0.020 0	0.367	0.400
	0.015 0	0.015 0	0.030 0	0.532	0.600
	0.020 0	0.020 0	0.040 0	0.706	0.800
Benzene	0.011 1	0.011 1	0.022 2	0.420	0.422
	0.012 0	0.012 0	0.024 0	0.457	0.480
	0.019 3	0.019 3	0.038 6	0.672	0.772
Nitrobenzene	0.013 9	0.013 9	0.027 8	0.545	0.556
	0.018 0	0.018 0	0.036 0	0.704	0.720
	0.021 4	0.021 4	0.042 8	0.810	0.856
Naphthalene	0.009 0	0.009 0	0.018 0	0.352	0.360
	0.010 3	0.010 3	0.020 6	0.415	0.412
	0.016 8	0.016 8	0.033 6	0.690	0.672
	0.016 6	0.018 1	0.034 7	0.635	0.694
<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	0.010 0	0.010 0	0.020 0	0.407	0.400
	0.020 0	0.020 0	0.040 0	0.757	0.800
Diphenylamine	0.005 0	0.005 0	0.010 0	0.204	0.200
	0.010 0	0.010 0	0.020 0	0.387	0.400
1,2-Dibromomethylene	0.010 0	0.010 0	0.020 0	0.388	0.400
	0.015 0	0.015 0	0.030 0	0.571	0.600
	0.020 0	0.020 0	0.040 0	0.740	0.800

degree of dissociation with dilution. The very low solubility of the iodine complexes in cyclohexane poses a question. How can one accurately measure very small depressions of the freezing point? It is felt that by using thermistors and a recorder, one may obtain an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}^\circ$. Such an apparatus for cryoscopic measurements will eliminate human errors to a great extent and make it possible to calculate the degree of dissociation and the equilibrium constants of iodine complexes. Nevitt¹⁹ and Ashby²⁰ previously used such an apparatus for cryoscopic measurements on polymers with great accuracy.

Spectroscopic study of iodine complexes: In order to detect complex formation and also to compare the donating power of individual donors, absorption of iodine complexes in the visible and uv region was studied (Tables 2-5).

Preparation of pure complexes between iodine and donors: It was possible to obtain the pyridine-iodine complex by evaporating a saturated solution of iodine in pyridine. Analysis showed a ratio of 1:1 for the two components. The substance showed m.p. 57-8°. The tetrahydrofuran-iodine complex was found to be extremely unstable at room temperature, and continuously losing THF to finally yield iodine. The aniline-iodine complex formed a solid solution in aniline; hence, it could not be separated.

TABLE 2— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ IODINE SOLUTIONS IN PURE SOLVENTS, ARRANGED IN DECREASING DEGREE OF INTERACTION

Solvent	λ_{max} (vis) nm	λ_{max} (uv) nm
Aniline	354	
Dimethylaniline	356	
Pyridine	369	
β -Picoline	370	
Tetrahydrofuran	443, 372, 366	
Nitrobenzene	488	297
1,2-Dibromoethylene	496	
Toluene	496	297
Benzene	496	297
Chlorobenzene	504	297
Cyclohexane	520	

TABLE 3— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ IODINE SOLUTIONS IN PRESENCE OF 1.0 M OF EACH OF THE FOLLOWING, ARRANGED IN DECREASING DEGREE OF INTERACTION

	λ_{max} nm
Tetrahydrofuran	486.5, 375, 356, 338
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	368, 342
Dimethylaniline	362
Aniline	374, 355
Pyridine	396.5
β -Picoline	412
Nitrobenzene	513
Toluene	515
1,2-Dibromoethylene	515
Benzene	516
Chlorobenzene	516
Phenol	516
Naphthalene	516

TABLE 4— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ IODINE SOLUTIONS IN PRESENCE OF 0.1 M OF EACH OF THE FOLLOWING, ARRANGED IN DECREASING DEGREE OF INTERACTION

	λ_{max} nm
Tetrahydrofuran	518, 375, 356, 338
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	390
Aniline	392, 376
Dimethylaniline	400
α -Naphthylamine	384
Pyridine	416
β -Picoline	436
Diphenylamine	512, 380
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	516, 377
Nitrobenzene	518
Benzene	519
Toluene	519
Chlorobenzene	519
Phenol	519
Naphthalene	519
<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	520, 358
2,4-Dinitrophenol	520, 350

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DILUTION ON IODINE COMPLEXES
Concn. of iodine for all solutions = $5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Donor	Molality of donor	λ_{max} (vis) nm	λ_{max} (uv) nm
Aniline	In pure solvent	354	
	1.0	374, 355	
	0.1	392, 376	
	0.01	520, 374	
Dimethylaniline	In pure solvent	356	
	1.0	362	
	0.1	400	
	0.01	519, 402	
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	In pure solvent	—	
	1.0	368, 342	
	0.1	390	
	0.01	517, 390	
Tetrahydrofuran	In pure solvent	443, 372, 366	
	1.0	486.5, 375, 356, 338	
	0.1	518, 375, 356, 338	
	0.01	520, 375, 356, 338	
Pyridine	In pure solvent	369	
	1.0	396.5	
	0.5	416	
	0.1	416	
	0.05	419	
	0.01	508, 418	
	0.005	509	
0.001	517		
β -Picoline	In pure solvent	370	
	1.0	412	
	0.1	436	
	0.01	518, 444	
Nitrobenzene	In pure solvent	488	297
	1.0	513	297
	0.1	518	297
	0.01	519	—
Benzene	In pure solvent	496	297
	1.0	516	297
	0.1	520	297
	0.01	520	—
Naphthalene	1.01	516	
	0.1	518	
	0.01	519	

Discussion

It can be seen clearly from the spectrometric measurements that the iodine complexes with various donors dissociate with increasing dilution. The free iodine peak slowly shifts to 520 nm. Benzene, nitrobenzene, chlorobenzene-iodine complexes show a peak at 297 nm in uv, which disappears at a mole-fraction (of the complex) of approximately 8×10^{-4} indicating almost complete dissociation of the complexes at that stage.

Donor molecules with a hetero atom in the molecule show much greater interaction with iodine as compared to that of benzene and alkylbenzenes. The nitro group on the benzene ring is an electron-withdrawing group, and hence is expected to decrease the electron density on the benzene ring. Still nitrobenzene shows slightly greater interaction with iodine than benzene does. This clearly shows that the electron donating effect for a hetero atom is much stronger than the π -electron density on the aromatic nucleus.

Aniline acts as a stronger solvating agent for iodine than nitrobenzene. This is expected, because the amino nitrogen is much more basic than the nitrogen atom of the nitro group. *N*-Alkylation of the amino group shows a slight decrease in the electron donating capacity of the nitrogen atom. If we compare the hetero atom in the ring, as in pyridine or picoline, with the free amino group, as in aniline, we see that the latter is a much stronger electro-donating group than the former. This is because the amino nitrogen atom has an electron pair that is less involved with the resonance in the aromatic nucleus than the nitrogen atom directly in the aromatic ring. Donor strengths of the hetero atoms nitrogen and oxygen in the ring can not be compared by taking pyridine and tetrahydrofuran as examples since the former substance is unsaturated and the latter is saturated.

Conclusions †

(i) Cryoscopic measurements on iodine complexes show great promise in determining the

degree of complexation, and the equilibrium constants of the complexes. However, there is a need of an apparatus to measure accurately small depressions in the freezing point. (ii) In order to detect the complex formation of iodine with aniline, dimethylaniline, *etc.*, one has to work with extremely low concentrations of complexes, ($< 1 \times 10^{-3} M$). (iii) In cyclohexane solution, iodine complexes with pyridine and picoline show much greater stability. (iv) The stronger interactions between iodine and donor occur when the solvent donor action is attributable mainly to particular atom, as in pyridine, picoline, aniline, THF, *etc.* (v) There is a direct relationship between the halogen solating capacity and the basicity of the solvent.

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